

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR SPIRITUAL-EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article explores the pedagogical conditions necessary for preparing students for spiritual and educational activities within the context of higher education in Uzbekistan. The importance of spiritual and moral development in national educational policy is emphasized through key legal and strategic documents. The study analyzes the concept of "pedagogical conditions" and identifies a set of principles essential for the effective organization of spiritual-educational processes, including creativity, naturalness, continuity, harmony, integrity, and cooperation. These principles are presented as a cohesive framework that fosters students' personal and professional development. The article also proposes a structured model consisting of goals, organized activities, and measurable outcomes, contributing to the improved quality of student preparation in the sphere of spiritual education.*

Keywords: *pedagogical conditions, spiritual and educational activity, higher education, moral upbringing, student preparation, creativity, continuity, cooperation, educational principles, Uzbekistan education system.*

It is well known that in the land of Turon, the spiritual development of individuals and the cultivation of moral values have always been a central concern of our ancestors. This task remains relevant today as well. Therefore, it is natural that in our country, the training of qualified teachers and mentors is regarded as a priority area. In particular, the following key documents emphasize the importance of enhancing the potential of specialists trained in the higher education system: The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PR-2909 dated April 20, 2017 about "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System", The Resolution No. PR-3907 dated August 14, 2018 about "On Measures to Raise the System of Educating Youth to be Spiritually, Morally and Physically Mature to a New Level of Quality", The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-637 dated September 23, 2020 about "On Education". These documents call for special attention to be paid to the qualifications and potential of specialists being trained in the higher education sector.

Improving the preparation of students for spiritual and educational activities, in turn, requires the clarification of pedagogical conditions. Pedagogical conditions are one of the main aspects of preparation for spiritual and educational activities, and dictionaries give three main meanings of the concept: 1) the environment in which something happens, 2) the space associated with the state of something, and 3) the rules included in a particular field of activity. Thus, the concept of "conditions" refers to the surrounding phenomena that interact with the subject, without which it cannot arise.

According to the concept of "pedagogical conditions", generalized in pedagogical literature, pedagogical conditions are classified as a set of measures of pedagogical influence (A.Ya. Nayn) that ensure that teachers and students achieve the level of formation of a healthy lifestyle culture.

The set of opportunities created for the purposeful implementation of pedagogical activities is considered pedagogical conditions, which together serve to determine the achievement of various stages of the result of educational processes and their effectiveness. The effectiveness of preparing students for spiritual and educational activities and achieving the desired results requires compliance with certain integral pedagogical conditions. The study identified the following pedagogical conditions for improving the preparation of students for spiritual and educational activities. The study also identified the principles of successful organization of spiritual and educational activities of students. In this process, some principles were identified as effective, based on A.M. Kuzmin's principles of organizing spiritual and educational activities, such as voluntariness in organizing types of spiritual and educational activities; orientation of the process of spiritual and educational activities to career selection; systematicity, coherence of didactics and other similar specific principles.

1. The principle of creativity. The content of this principle is to support innovative ideas and views during spiritual and educational activities, to encourage their positive thoughts and promising plans. The principle of dialogue, tolerance and reflective activity, implemented in the development of communicative competencies.

2. The principle of naturalness. The essence of the principle of naturalness is based on the recognition of the natural equality of people, the dignity and uniqueness of each person, and their integral unity with the environment. Taking this principle into account in preparing students for spiritual and educational activities ensured the effective implementation of this activity.

3. The principle of harmony of knowledge and skills, consciousness and behavior that students acquire during spiritual and educational activities. The principle of coherence consists in the requirement to organize activities in which students have the opportunity to check the practical nature of their activities and the correctness of the presentation.

4. The principle of continuity of education. This principle is aimed at consolidating the knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired in the educational process, as well as their systematic and consistent development.

5. The principle of integrity and consistency of spiritual and educational activities. The principle of integrity and consistency of spiritual and educational activities implies the perception and understanding of this activity as a whole system. For example, for educational processes taken in an abstract sense, this feature of integrity is the harmony of upbringing and education.

6. The principle of spiritual cooperation. Joint joy; positivism; cooperation; individuality. The principle of spiritual cooperation in spiritual and educational activities is based on the integrated use of all components of the educational process. This principle requires the organization of spiritual activities, taking into account all the factors involved in the educational process - family, educational institution, work team and society.

The use of these principles as a whole in preparing students for spiritual and educational activities gives effective results. The effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities requires that its implementation be in a certain system. For this purpose, the dissertation has formed a structure consisting of a target order, organized activities and expected results, which will serve to obtain effective results in preparing students for spiritual and educational activities.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 20 apreldagi “Oliy ta’lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-2909-sonli qarori.
2. Ожегов С. И. Толковый словарь русского языка : 100000 слов, терминов и выражений : [новое издание] / Сергей Иванович Ожегов ; под общ. ред. Л. И. Скворцова. — 28-е изд., перераб. — Москва : Мир И образование, 2015. — 1375, [1] с. : портр.; 22 см. — (Новые словари).; ISBN 978-5-94666-657-2
3. Найн А. Я. Педагогический эксперимент: методика и его организациa : учеб. пособие / А.Я. Найн, З.М. Уметбаев ; М-во образования Рос. Федерациa, Магнитог. гос. ун-т. — Магнитогорск: МаГУ, 2002 (Тип. МаГУ). — 125 с. : табл.; 20 см.
4. Кузмин А.М. Готовность учителя к воспитанию патриотизма подростков как педагогическая проблема / А.М. Кузмин, М.Г. Домбровская, Е.А. Сироткин // Вестник ЮУрГУ. Серия «Образование. Педагогические науки».
5. Ro`zieva D.I., Voxidova N.X., Xoliqova Z.M., Qurbonov A.A. Umumiy pedagogika nazariyasi va amaliyoti (Teoriya i praktika obshchey pedagogiki) O‘zbekiston Respublikasi intellektual mulk agentligining 2015 yil 17 noyabrda gi № DGU 03391raqamli guvohtonmasi.
6. Диссертация Казакова У.А. Дидактическая система профессиональной подготовки преподавателей технических вузов на основе интеграции педагогического и инженерного знания. file:///C:/Users/Nilufar/Downloads/autoref-didakticheskaya-sistema-professionalnoi-podgotovki-prepodavatelei-tekhnicheskikh-vuzov-na.pdf
7. International Scientific Journal SCIENCE AND INNOVATION. Series B volume 2 issue 11 – 721p. <https://scientists.uz/uploads/journal/202311B.pdf>